

A temporal model of territorial defence with antagonistic interactions

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Abstract

Territorial behaviour is an important part of the lives of many animals. Once a territory has been acquired, an animal may spend its entire life on it, and may have to repeatedly defend it from conspecifics. Some species make great investments in the defence of a territory, and this defence can be costly, in terms of time, energy and risk of injury. Time costs in particular have rarely been explicitly factored into such models. In this paper we consider a model of territorial defence which includes both population dynamic and time delay elements, building upon recent advances in time constraint models. Populations may divide into two distinct types, where one type makes no effort to control territories. We shall call this type nomads, and the other type territorials. Here the territory owners must divide their time between patrolling and foraging, and this balance is their only strategic decision. We show how to find the evolutionarily stable patrolling strategy and the population composition of territorials and nomads, and consider some examples demonstrating key situations. We see that both time constraints and population density pressure are crucial to influencing behaviour. In particular we find cases with both territorial individuals and nomads where a mixed, either pure or both pure patrolling strategies are evolutionarily stable. In different conditions either nomads or territorials can be absent, and indeed for a significant range of parameter combinations the population can exhibit tristability, with three distinct ecologically stable population compositions: with both nomads and territorials, only nomads or only territorials.

Keywords: evolutionary game theory, territoriality, time constraints, owner-intruder games, density dependence

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1 Introduction

Territory is the sociographical area that an animal defends against conspecifics (Adams 2001, Hinsch and Komdeur 2017, Owen-Smith 1977). The evolutionary success of territorial behaviour is determined by the benefits and costs of occupying and defending the territory. Direct benefits include: a) more or less exclusive access to food (Maher and Lott 1995); b) mating opportunities (Sinervo and Lively 1996, Sinervo et al. 2000, Stamps 1987); c) the females deter infanticide (Ostfeld 1990); d) a refuge from predators (Cowlshaw 1997, Everett et al. 1993, Maher and Lott 1995); e) domiciles (e.g. a nest, burrows). There are also indirect benefits, such as the fact that non-owner individuals have limited breeding capability (e.g. Boutin and Schweiger 1988, Stamps 1994) and potentially limited access to food. The cost of territory ownership can be measured in the probability of death, energy loss and time duration of fighting (Grant et al. 1992) and patrolling. Patrolling can include searching, fighting, scent marking (Schlägel 2017) and any combination of these (Corbet 2004, Golab 2017). Territorial patrolling is costly, requiring both energy and time. For instance, 58% of the total travelling time of chimpanzees is patrolling (Amsler 2010) and dragonflies devote about 20% of their total flight time to patrolling (Parr 1983).

Since all of the costs of territory ownership comes from interaction with conspecifics, only game-theoretical models can give insight into the evolutionary stability of territoriality (for a review see e.g. Hinsch and Komdeur 2017). Fights occur between neighbours and between owners and individuals with no territory (“floaters”), and are often modelled using the Hawk-Dove game (Hinsch and Komdeur 2010, Kokko et al. 2006, Maynard Smith 1982, Mesterton-Gibbons and Adams 2003, Pereira et al. 2003) including using explicit strategies related to ownership (e.g. the bourgeois strategy, see Maynard Smith 1982, Eshel and Sansone 1995, Grafen 1987). The interaction between neighbours is well studied (Hinsch and Komdeur 2017), for instance when the cost of interaction is high enough, then fights between neighbours occur with low intensity and low cost compared to interactions between owners and intruders (Morrell and Kokko 2005, see also the “dear enemy hypothesis” Getty 1987, Temeles 1994). On the other hand, interactions between owners and floaters can draw our attention to two components of territoriality. Firstly, if the density of floaters is high enough, then irrespective of whether the floaters either avoid fights or are ready to fight, the owner has to spend time and energy either chasing the non-fighter away or beating the aggressive floaters out of its territory. In both cases the owner spends much time defending its territory, consequently the owner has less time for mating and feeding, thus its fitness will be decreased by too many interactions when the intrusion rate is high enough. Furthermore, patrolling also takes extra, e.g. traveling, time. Moreover, territoriality as a competitive behaviour can decrease the total density of the population when owners can monopolize more food than what they really need. Thus, territoriality has a role in population regulation (Brown 1969). Secondly, the density of the non-aggressive floaters depends on whether the owners can or cannot shut floaters out of their territories, and consequently deprive floaters of the chance to breed (Stamps 1994). In this paper we concentrate on these two components of territoriality: the time constraints of owning and defending a territory and the density dependence of interactions (e.g. Both and Visser 2003, Houston and McNamara 2006, Lopez-Sepulcre and Kokko 2005). We discuss these two concepts in turn below.

Time constraints in ecology have important consequences. For instance, in trophic interactions the functional response takes account of time constraints (Holling 1959, Křivan 2008, Garay 2019). Schoener (1987), in the framework of a detailed optimization model, calculate the optimal territory size and patrolling time, as a function of food density and intrusion rate, calling our attention to the importance of the time budget. More recently, time constraints have been considered in game-theoretical models, especially in connection to food-stealing behaviour. Broom and Ruxton (1998) developed a game-theoretic model of kleptoparasitism where individuals could strategically challenge for food, but where contests took time that could be spent searching (e.g. see also Broom et al. 2004, Broom and Rychtář 2011). This model was fitted to a population of foraging

gulls in Spencer and Broom (2018). Such competition over food has similarities and differences to territorial contests. In both cases there is an owner and a challenger (or indeed perhaps more than one challenger, as in Broom and Rychtář 2011) competing for a resource. The value of a territory is likely to be much greater than a food item, leading to more significant (longer, more violent) contests. It may be logical to concede a food item rather than fight, as there is the possibility of finding another uncontested item. For territories, however, there are unlikely to be uncontested ones, and so it is more likely to be better to stay and fight (Morrell and Kokko 2005, Hinsch and Komdeur 2017).

Furthermore, the theory of single-species matrix games under time constraints has been developed (Garay et al. 2017, see also Křivan and Cressman 2017, Cressman and Křivan 2019). Here each interaction has two consequences: a benefit and a waiting time (during which the players are not able to interact) and the concept of a (monomorphic) evolutionarily stable strategy (ESS) in such games was characterized. The common assumption of these game theoretical models is that the individual actions (e.g. fights) exclude each other, e.g., at a particular time each individual is either searching or fighting but cannot do these two activities simultaneously.

As mentioned above, a second important component of the model to understand territoriality is density dependence and its relationship with evolutionary stability. Density dependent evolutionary monomorphic stability for multi-species co-evolutionary ecosystems was introduced in Cressman and Garay (2003a,b). This notion is strictly based on the dynamical perspective; here an ecological equilibrium of a system remains stable when a rare mutant phenotype is introduced in each species and subsequently eliminated according to the population dynamics.

The game theoretical literature of territorial behaviour (starting from the Hawk Dove game) mainly concentrates on the aggressive interactions between owner and intruder (e.g. Morrell and Kokko 2005, Hinsch and Komdeur 2017 and the references within). However, the evolutionary stability of territoriality cannot be fully understood without considering an alternative type of individual, which has no territory and pursues an alternative strategy without striving for territory ownership, and consequently which is free from all costs of the acquisition or ownership of a territory. Whilst the ownership of a territory can guarantee that a male can mate with the females in the territory, the territory owner is not always able to exclude other males from mating with these females.

Fighting over territories will lead to the evolution of enhanced fighting abilities, but these will usually come at some cost, for example larger body size or heavy weapons which require greater resources. Similarly there can be a range of behaviours that an animal can use in defence of its territory depending upon the value of the territory and the frequency or severity of potential invasions. Often the alternative strategy that we mention above can then become viable; namely not to compete for territories at all, and thus dispense with the extra resources required to be an effective competitor. Some species can then diversify into different types with different physical forms, adapted to either fighting for territories or obtaining resources in an alternative way.

For instance, a well-known example is that of the side-blotched lizard (*Uta stansburiana*). Ultra-dominant orange-throated males establish and control large territories, but are not able to prevent the yellow stripe-throated males ("sneakers") from mating with "their" females (Sinervo and Lively 1996, Sinervo et al. 2000). Here the main point is that the yellow stripe-throated males do not, and never will, have a territory. Similar phenomena take place in the case of sunfish and salmon (e.g. Gross 1984 and references therein, Gross and Charnov 1980). Thus we will consider a non-territorial phenotype, called a nomad, which has no territory and does not get involved in fights.

The paper is organised as follows. In Section 2 we explain our model. In Section 3 we find the "right" strategy for our population, i.e. find the Nash equilibrium strategy. In Section 4 we consider the stability of such a population against potential invading "mutants" of an alternative type. Finally in Section 5 we discuss our results and future work.

2 The Model

In this section we consider the details of the model, introducing the biological scenario, the mathematical details and the parameters and develop the analysis for a “resident” population where a single strategy (as later defined) occurs.

2.1 The biological scenario

We consider a population in which there are two types of individual that we shall term territorials and nomads. As previously described these could be male individuals who aim to secure mates either by owning a territory which can support a group of females (the territorial individuals) or by an opportunistic strategy which involves mating with females wherever the opportunity arises. Alternatively the resources could be food, and it is the latter case that we shall use in the terminology that follows.

Nomad individuals wander through the field regardless of the territory borders looking for prey. If they come across a territory owner they flee. The two styles of living exclude one another. A territorial individual having a territory (i.e. an owner) lives on its territory which it never leaves. It defends the territory against intruding territorials and nomads or hunts for prey inside the territory. A territorial individual without a territory (i.e. an intruder) looks to challenge for a territory and for prey to consume. If it comes across a territorial individual having a territory then they fight over the territory and the winner gets the territory while the loser becomes/remains an intruder.

An owner can follow one of the two pure strategies:

The *patroller strategy*: the owner looks for intruders. It does not find any prey, but it successfully defends its territory with a higher probability than the owners following the other pure strategy below. Then its intake derives only from a background intake which every owner has (this could be a share of prey captured by subordinate groupmates within the territory).

The *predator strategy*: the owner looks for prey. Therefore, an intake from the prey comes in addition to the background intake but the owner successfully defends its territory with a lower probability than when following the patroller strategy.

We are interested in which strategy will evolve in the population. To investigate this question we have to calculate the fitnesses of our different types, which will depend upon their densities within the population. We use two approaches, that operate on different timescales. The first is a population dynamic model similar to the Lotka-Volterra equations which describes the evolution of the nomads and territorials by differential equations (the slower process). This involves game-theoretical fitness terms derived following the second approach using the methodology of Garay et al. (2017), which considers a stochastic behavioural dynamics process of individuals moving between population states for any given population composition (the faster process).

2.2 Population terminology and parameters

Here we consider the key terminology and parameters of the model, breaking it down into distinct parts based upon the different aspects of the model.

2.2.1 Population densities

We assume that the population follows a stochastic process moving between a number of states. We shall consider this in detail in Section 2.3. The population density of the nomads is denoted by x and of the territorials is denoted by y , scaled to the number of territories, i.e. the population density of territories is 1. Equivalently y is the number of territorial individuals per territory, and x is the number of nomads per territory. Thus if $y \leq 1$ there are enough territories for all territorials to have one, but if $y > 1$ there are not, and they have to contest them. It is x and y which evolve

on the slow timescale (we shall see how to find the values of x and y in Section 2.4), and for the purposes of the faster stochastic model, these can be considered fixed.

Table 1: The model parameters and notation

Parameter	Meaning
x, y, z	Density of nomads, resident and mutant territorials
ϱ_n	Proportion of active nomads among nomads
ϱ_o	Proportion of active owners among owners
ϱ_a	Proportion of active patrollers among patrollers
ϱ_r	Proportion of active predators among predators
ϱ_i	Proportion of active intruders among intruders
b	Steady contribution in the intake rate of an owner
i_h	Benefit gained from a prey
c_w, c_l	Cost of injury of the winner/loser in a fight
c_f	Cost of fleeing
t_w, t_l	Duration of regeneration after winning/losing a fight
t_h	Time necessary to handling a prey
α_a, α_r	Probability that a patroller/predator wins a fight
d	Cost rate of maintenance
c_{nn}	Cost rate of nomads on nomads indirect interaction
c_{nt}	Cost rate of nomads on territorials indirect interaction
c_{tn}	Cost rate of territorials on nomads indirect interaction
c_{tt}	Cost rate of territorials on territorials indirect interaction
λ_i	Rate of finding an active intruder
λ_o	Rate of finding an active owner
λ_h	Rate of finding a prey
λ_r	Rate of reconsidering the state without fight
f	Normalized rate of encountering a territory
p, q, r	Probability of choosing the predator state for residents/mutants
F	Fitness of an average nomad
G	Fitness of an average resident territorial
H	Fitness of an average mutant territorial

2.2.2 Events and time constraints

Here we shall introduce some parameters and concepts. Each individual can be involved in a number of different activities, which can provide some reward or cost, and in turn can lead onto other activities. We first describe the activities and their (expected) durations below, before considering the rewards and costs.

Time constraints: If an individual is busy with fighting, handling a prey or fleeing, respectively, then it cannot be involved in another activity (fighting or fleeing or hunting), and we assume that it is effectively invisible for individuals searching for a fighting partner or prey. Such an individual is considered to be *inactive* while an individual in the searching state is considered to be *active*. This, for example, means that if a territory owner looks for intruders then it can only encounter those intruders or nomads which are active. Therefore the probability of an encounter with territorial intruders or nomads is proportional to the density of active territorial intruders and nomads rather than the total density of territorial intruders and nomads.

$\varrho_o, \varrho_i, \varrho_n, \varrho_a, \varrho_r$ are the proportion of active (i.e. searching), individuals among the territorial owners, the intruder territorials, nomads, territorial owners in the patroller state and territorial

owners in the p[re]dator state (see below for a detailed explanation), respectively. These are not fixed parameters, but depend upon y in our model, and we shall evaluate them explicitly in Section 2.3.5.

Different encounters cost specific expected amounts of time (which might be 0). In each case we assume an exponentially distributed length of time with the following means. We have:

t_h is the expected time length of handling the prey,

t_f the expected time length for a nomad to flee from a territory owner,

t_w (t_l) the expected time length of regeneration after winning (losing) a territory owner versus intruder fight, i.e. the time depends only upon the outcome of the fight, and not the initial state of the individual concerned. For losing this could include some fleeing time, as above. For simplicity the time of the fight itself is assumed to be zero (alternatively this could be non-zero and included in the winning/losing regeneration times).

2.2.3 Rewards and costs

Depending upon whether an individual owns a territory and on what events occur, there are a number of rewards and costs that they can receive. These are as follows:

b is a steady (baseline) contribution in the expected intake rate of an owner. This is the main benefit of having a territory. This can derive from, for example, the fact that the owner knows its territory better or one can imagine the owner as a leader of a group, for instance a male in a pride of lions, and the group provide the significant benefit of a steady supply of food, giving the contribution b in the expected intake rate. An alternative is where the reward is in terms of mating opportunities, and an owning male has (almost) exclusive access to a group of females, and this also applies in the lion example. i_h is the benefit gained from consuming a prey item.

c_w is the cost of the injury to the winner in a fight.

c_l is the cost of the injury to the loser in a fight.

c_f is the cost of fleeing.

There are also indirect costs which do not relate directly to the interactions, but come about through independent effects.

d is the cost rate (cost per time) of maintenance; all individuals consume resources simply to stay alive, and these are then not available for reproduction.

c_{nn}, c_{nt}, c_{tn} and c_{tt} are the cost rates of indirect interactions; these are the costs of nomads on nomads, nomads on territorials, territorials on nomads and territorials on territorials, respectively. This derives from the fact that the general environmental resources (e.g. water, air, place and so on) used by the individuals are bounded. One can think that the more individuals there are the harder it is to obtain the given environmental resources or the worse the quality of the environmental resources are, and that different types of individuals can have different effects.

2.3 The stochastic process

In our model we consider an ecological system of two types which evolves over a considerable period of time (following the differential equation model that we shall introduce in Section 2.4), so that the values of x and y change as individuals are born and die. We assume that this process happens on a much slower timescale than that involving interactions between individuals, where it can be assumed that over the course of this process, x and y do not change.

To give the terms deriving from direct interactions we follow the Markov model of Garay et al. (2017). Different events (hunting, fighting) can happen to an individual. The events have rates which give how often they can be expected to occur (as if the time between two events of the same type were an exponential random variable) and events have durations which are also assumed to be an exponential random variable. Whilst an event occurs, other events cannot occur. Furthermore every event leads to some (maybe negative or zero) intake for the individual. An individual in the

searching state experiences any given event at some rate (some time will elapse before an event occurs). If the individual experiences an event then the event takes its (expected) time and when the event finishes the individual starts to search again. Since the rate at which events occur, the duration of events and the intakes derived from the events vary with the events, we calculate an average time length for an event to happen and an associated average intake per event. The expected intake rate is then calculated as the quotient of these two values.

Formally, assume that there are n different events with rates $\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_n$. Their lengths are t_1, \dots, t_n and the intakes are i_1, \dots, i_n . Denote by Λ the sum $\sum_k \lambda_k$. Then we calculate the fitness as the expected intake per event divided by the expected time per event, i.e.

$$\frac{\sum_{k=1}^n \frac{\lambda_k}{\Lambda} i_k}{\frac{1}{\Lambda} + \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{\lambda_k}{\Lambda} t_k} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^n \lambda_k i_k}{1 + \sum_{k=1}^n \lambda_k t_k}. \quad (2.1)$$

Note that $1/\Lambda$ corresponds to the average searching time and λ_k/Λ is the probability of the k -th event occurring.

Accordingly, since we know the rewards/costs and times associated with each activity, we can calculate the part of the fitness deriving from direct interactions (owning a territory, consuming prey, fighting and fleeing), which we do in Section 2.4.

2.3.1 Transitions and rewards for territory owners

An owner chooses the **patroller state** with probability p in every reconsideration event (see below). In this state, it only gains rewards through the steady background intake rate b . However the owner defeats intruders with a higher probability because, for example, it is more difficult to surprise it. The value of p is the only strategic element within the model. We consider the possible events which can occur depending on the chosen strategy.

An active patroller can encounter the following events:

To find an active intruder with rate $\lambda_i = f \rho_i [1 - \min(1, 1/y)] y$, where f is the rate at which any given active intruder encounters a territory (we will call f the *unit rate*). Here if $y \leq 1$, all territorials have a territory and so there can be no intruder, if $y > 1$, the density of territorials without territories is $y - 1$. When they meet, they fight for the territory. The defeated individual will be without a territory and gets injured, which is considered as a negative intake $-c_l$. The winner obtains the territory but also potentially gets injured which means an intake $-c_w$. The duration of the regeneration process is t_w after winning a fight whilst it is t_l after losing a fight (the duration of the fight itself is assumed to be 0). After a fight, the territory owner (either the original owner or the new owner if the intruder wins) will reconsider its state, and will select the patroller state with probability p . We cannot distinguish the winner from the original owner (the owner before the fight). It can be the original owner or the original intruder but this does not matter from the view of the territorial population; the winner will always be the owner after the fight, and the loser will always be an intruder. A patroller owner wins with probability α_a .

To find an active nomad with rate $\lambda_n = f \rho_n x$. For simplicity, the event needs no time and means zero intake for the owner, that is, nomads have no direct effect on territorial owners. Accordingly, no term corresponding to this event occurs in the formula describing the fitness deriving from direct interactions (see Section 2.4.1).

To reconsider the state: the owner can reconsider its search strategy (patroller or predator) with rate λ_r , again choosing patroller with probability p . We note that this is the second way a reconsideration can happen, as it also happens after a fight (as described above).

An owner chooses the **predator state** with probability $1 - p$. The word ‘‘predator’’ refers to the fact that the owner searches not only for intruders but for prey which are a further positive intake in addition to the steady background intake rate b . However, in return, the owner wins the fight with a lower probability.

An active predator can encounter the following events:

To find a prey with rate λ_h . The intake is i_h and the time necessary for handling the prey is t_h .

To find an active intruder with rate λ_i . The scenario is the same for the patroller case except that the owner wins with probability α_r instead of α_a .

There are two further events each of which occur in an identical way to those for the patroller. Namely:

To find an active nomad with rate λ_n .

To reconsider the state with rate λ_r independently of finding something.

2.3.2 Transitions and rewards for territory intruders

A *territorial intruder* looks for prey and for the opportunity to acquire a territory. An intruder encounters the following events:

To find an active owner with rate $\lambda_o = f \varrho_o \min(1, 1/y)y$. The event is discussed above (see the owner in the patroller state).

To find prey with rate λ_h . The intake is i_h and the time necessary for handling the prey is t_h .

To find an active nomad/territorial intruder with rate λ_n and λ_i , respectively. For simplicity, the events needs no time and means zero intake for the intruder, that is, nomads/intruders have no direct effect on territorial intruders (accordingly, no term corresponding to these events occurs in the formula describing the fitness for intruders deriving from direct interactions).

2.3.3 Transitions and rewards for nomads

A *nomad* looks for prey. If it encounters a territory owner then it first flees, and only after that starts a new searching phase. A nomad can encounter the following events:

To find an active owner with rate λ_o . Then the nomad flees. Fleeing takes a time t_f and costs c_f

To find prey with rate λ_h . The intake is i_h and the time necessary for handling the prey is t_h .

To find an active nomad/territorial intruder with rate λ_n and λ_i , respectively. For simplicity, the events need no time and mean zero intake for the nomad, that is nomads/intruders have no direct effect on nomads. Accordingly, no term corresponding to these events occurs in the formula describing the fitness for nomads deriving from direct interactions.

2.3.4 Pairwise interactions

In the above, there are a number of possible interactions; each of owners, intruders and nomads can meet others who are owners, intruders or nomads (except that as owners never leave their territory, owners cannot meet other owners). As described above, meetings between intruders or nomads with intruders or nomads have no effect on the payoff. This leaves four key interactions. Owners meeting intruders, owners meeting nomads, intruders meeting owners, and nomads meeting owners.

In the above we have used the same unit rate f in all four of these expressions. In fact this is a natural (and in some cases necessary) assumption. Suppose that f_i was the unit rate for the intruders meeting owners and f_o was the unit rate for the owners meeting intruders. Since the total rate of active owners meeting active intruders must be the same as the total rate of active intruders meeting active owners (if I meet you, you must meet me) we have

$$\underbrace{f_i \varrho_i [y - \min(1, y)]}_{\lambda_i} \varrho_o \min(1, y) = \underbrace{f_o \varrho_o \min(1, y)}_{\lambda_o} \varrho_i [y - \min(1, y)].$$

We infer that $f_i = f_o$.

A similar argument holds for the unit rates for owners meeting nomads and nomads meeting owners. It could be that this meeting rate is different to that from above, but for simplicity we assume that all four unit rates are the same.

2.3.5 Calculating the active state probabilities

We still need to calculate the probability that a given type of individual is active (i.e. is searching). An individual is active with some probability, say ϱ , and we assume if we take a glance at the population then we find that the ϱ part of the population is active as if the individuals were active or inactive independently of each other (there is no synchronization in the population such as everybody is inactive at night), and the size of the population tended to infinity. This assumption is a condition in the model of Garay et al. (2017). Hence we have the active part of p territorial owners being in the patroller state is

$$\varrho_a = \frac{\frac{1}{\lambda_r + \lambda_i}}{\frac{1}{\lambda_r + \lambda_i} + \frac{\lambda_i}{\lambda_r + \lambda_i} t_w} = \frac{1}{1 + \lambda_i t_w},$$

the active part of $1 - p$ territorial owners being in predator state is

$$\varrho_r = \frac{\frac{1}{\lambda_r + \lambda_i}}{\frac{1}{\lambda_r + \lambda_i} + \frac{\lambda_i}{\lambda_r + \lambda_i} t_w + \frac{\lambda_h}{\lambda_r + \lambda_i} t_h} = \frac{1}{1 + \lambda_i t_w + \lambda_h t_h},$$

the active part of territory owners is

$$\begin{aligned} \varrho_o &= \frac{p \frac{1}{\lambda_r + \lambda_i} + (1 - p) \frac{1}{\lambda_r + \lambda_i}}{p \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_r + \lambda_i} + \frac{\lambda_i}{\lambda_r + \lambda_i} t_w \right) + (1 - p) \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_r + \lambda_i} + \frac{\lambda_i}{\lambda_r + \lambda_i} t_w + \frac{\lambda_h}{\lambda_r + \lambda_i} t_h \right)} \\ &= \frac{1}{1 + \lambda_i t_w + (1 - p) \lambda_h t_h}, \end{aligned} \quad (2.2)$$

the active part of territorial intruders is

$$\varrho_i = \frac{\frac{1}{\lambda_o + \lambda_h}}{\frac{1}{\lambda_o + \lambda_h} + \frac{\lambda_o}{\lambda_o + \lambda_h} t_l + \frac{\lambda_h}{\lambda_o + \lambda_h} t_h} = \frac{1}{1 + \lambda_o t_l + \lambda_h t_h}, \quad (2.3)$$

the active part of nomads is

$$\varrho_n = \frac{1}{1 + \lambda_o t_f + \lambda_h t_h}.$$

2.4 Population dynamics and the fitness functions

As stated in Section 2.2.1, x is the density of nomads (the number of nomad individuals per territory) and y is the density of territorial individuals (the number of territorial individuals per territory).

We interpret the fitness as a reproductive rate. Consider the following model:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x} &= xF(x, y) \\ \dot{y} &= yG(x, y) \end{aligned} \quad (2.4)$$

where F and G , respectively, correspond to the fitness of an average nomad and an average territorial, respectively. The fitness functions (F, G) above include the effect of direct interactions (hunting, fighting, fleeing), indirect interactions (using common environmental resources) and maintenance. Note that such a differential equation model focuses on only the biomass of the population but not the different individuals. The individuals of the same type can not be distinguished from each other. The death of an individual hence simply means a decrease of the biomass.

To calculate G and F we follow Garay et al. (2017). As previously stated, we assume that the stochastic process governing direct interactions happens on a faster timescale to the population dynamic process, so that we assume here that x and y are effectively constant. In this period (call

it the foraging season), the individuals gather/lose the energy which can be used to reproduce. This time is long enough to reach a stationary state; moreover, the time when the population is not in the stationary state is negligible. After this period comes a period (call it the breeding season) when gained/lost rewards are transformed into births and deaths. The model (2.4) describes the long-term evolutionary consequences of many foraging seasons and breeding seasons in turn. We assume that the fitness of an individual (or the biomass of individuals of the same type) for a given breeding season is determined in the previous foraging season.

2.4.1 The direct interaction fitnesses

By formula (2.1), the term representing the direct interactions in the fitness of a nomad, a component of fitness F , is:

$$\frac{\lambda_h i_h - \lambda_o c_f}{1 + \lambda_o t_f + \lambda_h t_h}. \quad (2.5)$$

Similarly, by (2.1) we get the following terms in the fitness G deriving from direct interactions: The term representing the direct interactions of a territorial owner in the patroller state is

$$D_a = b + \frac{-\lambda_i c_w}{1 + \lambda_i t_w}.$$

The term representing the direct interactions of a territorial owner in the predator state is

$$D_r = b + \frac{-\lambda_i c_w + \lambda_h i_h}{1 + \lambda_i t_w + \lambda_h t_h}.$$

Before giving the term representing the direct interactions of a territorial intruder we need to know the proportion of patrollers and predators, respectively, among the territorial owners. We know that an owner can reconsider its strategy only if there is a reconsideration event, or at the end of a fight (recall that it does not matter who is defeated in the fight because the winner is indistinguishable from the original owner for an outside observer). Hence the time from a reconsideration event until the next reconsideration event in the patroller state is

$$T_a = \frac{1}{\lambda_r + \lambda_i} + \frac{\lambda_i}{\lambda_r + \lambda_i} t_w = \frac{1 + \lambda_i t_w}{\lambda_r + \lambda_i},$$

whilst in the predator state, this is

$$T_r = \frac{1}{\lambda_r + \lambda_i} + \frac{\lambda_i}{\lambda_r + \lambda_i} t_w + \frac{\lambda_h}{\lambda_r + \lambda_i} t_h = \frac{1 + \lambda_i t_w + \lambda_h t_h}{\lambda_r + \lambda_i}.$$

Therefore, in the stationary state, a randomly chosen owner is in the patroller state with probability

$$\frac{p T_a}{p T_a + (1 - p) T_r} = \frac{p \frac{1 + \lambda_i t_w}{\lambda_r + \lambda_i}}{p \frac{1 + \lambda_i t_w}{\lambda_r + \lambda_i} + (1 - p) \frac{1 + \lambda_i t_w + \lambda_h t_h}{\lambda_r + \lambda_i}} = \frac{p(1 + \lambda_i t_w)}{1 + \lambda_i t_w + (1 - p)\lambda_h t_h} =: \pi \quad (2.6)$$

and it is in predator state with probability $1 - \pi$. Hence the term representing the direct interactions of a territorial intruder is

$$D_i = \frac{-f \min(1, y) [\varrho_a \pi c_l + \varrho_r (1 - \pi) c_l] + \lambda_h i_h}{1 + \lambda_o t_l + \lambda_h t_h}. \quad (2.7)$$

Note that $\lambda_o = f \min(1, y) \varrho_o = f \min(1, y) [\pi \varrho_a + (1 - \pi) \varrho_r]$.

Now that we know D_a, D_r and D_i we can find the term representing the direct interactions in the fitness of a “mean” territorial as

$$\begin{aligned} D(y) &= \frac{1}{y} \{ \min(1, y) [\pi D_a + (1 - \pi) D_r] + [y - \min(1, y)] D_i \} \\ &= \begin{cases} \pi D_a + (1 - \pi) D_r & \text{if } y \leq 1 \\ \frac{1}{y} [\pi D_a + (1 - \pi) D_r + (y - 1) D_i] & \text{if } y > 1 \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (2.8)$$

After substitution ($\lambda_i = f[y - \min(1, y)] \varrho_i$, $\lambda_o = f[y - \min(1, y)] \varrho_o = f[y - \min(1, y)] [\pi \varrho_a + (1 - \pi) \varrho_r]$) we get, if $y \leq 1$ (note that $\lambda_i = 0$ now) then

$$D(y) = b + (1 - \pi) \frac{\lambda_h i_h}{1 + \lambda_h t_h};$$

if $y > 1$ then

$$D(y) = \frac{b}{y} - \frac{f}{y} (y - 1) \varrho_i \varrho_o (c_w + c_l) + \frac{(1 - \pi) \varrho_r + (y - 1) \varrho_i}{y} \lambda_h i_h. \quad (2.9)$$

Note when $y \leq 1$ the term D is independent of y .

2.4.2 Evaluating G and F

The simpler part of the fitness derives from the indirect interactions and maintenance. The former is considered as a term $-c_{nt}x - c_{tt}y$ and $-c_{nn}x - c_{tn}y$, respectively, the latter as term $-d$. These terms are present both in F and G .

Now using the stochastic process described in Section 2.3 we can give the concrete shape of G . Note that when we calculate G we would like to get the fitness of a unit of territorial biomass rather than the fitness of a given territorial individual so G can be considered as the expected fitness of a randomly chosen territorial individual.

Using the equations (2.5) and (2.9) we get the following formulae for the fitnesses G and F :

$$\begin{aligned} G &= G(x, y) = -d - c_{nt}x - c_{tt}y + D(y), \\ F &= F(x, y) = -d - c_{nn}x - c_{tn}y + \frac{\lambda_h i_h - \lambda_o c_f}{1 + \lambda_o t_f + \lambda_h t_h}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.10)$$

2.4.3 The steady states of the dynamical system

For any particular territorial strategy p , we can now follow the evolution of the system (2.4) to its steady states. As we shall see in the examples in the next section, there can be more than one steady state to the system. In any given steady state, (x^*, y^*) , we will have specific values of x and y that can be used in any of the components of the payoff function and we will thus be able to consider the evolutionary stability of the strategy p which led to this steady state. We shall first consider some examples.

2.5 Examples

In this section we consider some example with a stable interior equilibrium in which both nomads and territorials are present in the system with positive density and with stable equilibria when only one of them are present with positive density. It is important to emphasize that there are no mutants in the territorial population in the present section, the population of territorials is monomorphic and we only investigate whether an ecological equilibrium nomads and territorials is

possible with respect to the dynamics (2.4). Later we analyze what occurs if some mutants appear in the territorial population at the interior equilibrium.

In each example the corresponding differential equation system given in (2.4) has a stable interior ecological equilibrium and, in some cases, there are two further stable equilibria in which there are no nomads or no territorials so these cases show ecological tristability. In the equilibrium containing territorials the density of them is greater than 1 which means that there are both owners and intruders in the territorial population. In this paper we principally focus on the “upper part” of the phase space, that is, when $y \geq 1$. However, to get an example for an equilibrium in which the density of the territorials is zero we have also investigated the $y < 1$ case.

To find appropriate parameters we have used a computer algebra (Mathematica 11.3) which is capable of symbolic calculations. Thus our results are exact. We consider six examples below, each of which demonstrate a distinct situation:

1. Parameters: $f = 1/10$, $\lambda_h = 4/25$, $t_h = t_f = t_w = t_l = 0$, $c_w = 1/15$, $c_l = 1/4$, $c_f = 1/10$, $c_{tn} = 1/100$, $c_{tt} = 1/1000$, $c_{nn} = 1/600$, $c_{nt} = 1/250$, $i_h = 3/10$, $d = 1/1000$, $\alpha_a = 9/10$, $\alpha_r = 1/2$ and $b = 21/100$. The patrolling strategy for this example is $p = 15475/19208$.
2. The parameters are the same as in Example 1, except that $b = 205/1000$ and $p = 0$.
3. The parameters are the same as in Example 1, except that $b = 215/1000$ and $p = 1$.
4. Parameters: $f = 1/10$, $\lambda_h = 4/25$, $t_h = t_f = t_w = t_l = 0$, $c_w = 1/15$, $c_l = 1/4$, $c_f = 1/10$, $c_{tn} = c_{tt} = c_{nn} = c_{nt} = 1/300$, $i_h = 4/10$, $d = 1/500$, $\alpha_a = 9/10$, $\alpha_r = 1/2$ and $b = 1/10$. The patrolling strategy for this example is $p = 25/128$.
5. The parameters are the same as in Example 4, except that $p = 0$.
6. The parameters are the same as in Example 4, except that $p = 1$.

2.5.1 Examples for ecological tristability (Examples 1-3)

As stated above, most parameters for Examples 1-3 are identical. The only distinction in the parameters is in the value of the steady contribution b in the expected intake rate of an owner (although the strategies of the territorials also differ, as we discuss below). As we see, there is no particular effect of this distinction in the present section but the significance will be seen when the resistance to mutants is investigated.

The corresponding phase portraits are shown on Figure 1-3: Figure 1 belongs to Example 1, Figure 2 belongs to Example 2 and Figure 3 belongs to Example 3. The strategy of the territorial individuals p varies with the example considered, and has always been chosen in such a way that the population of individuals following this strategy can resist mutants of any kind.

The three diagrams are very similar, each having five hyperbolic¹ equilibria (see Table 2): an asymptotically stable equilibrium on the y -axis, two interior unstable equilibria, an interior asymptotically stable equilibrium and an asymptotically stable equilibrium on the x -axis, so there is an ecological tristability. We can see later, the stable interior equilibrium (which is our main interest) remains stable with respect to the extended dynamics (4.4) in all of the three examples.

¹Recall that an equilibrium is hyperbolic with respect to a dynamics if the Jacobian matrix of the dynamics at the equilibrium has no eigenvalues with zero real parts. Then the stability of the equilibrium can simply be determined from the signs of the real parts of the eigenvalues.

Figure 1: The phase portrait of the system (2.4) with parameters of Example 1 (see the main text) when $b = 21/100$ and $p = 15475/19208$. There are five equilibria marked by black discs on the diagram; each of them is hyperbolic and three of them are stable, that is, there is an ecological tristability. The coordinates of the equilibria in the ascending order of the first coordinates are $(0, 23.85)$, $(3.33, 7.86)$, $(19.51, 1.12)$, $(21.76, 0.77)$, $(28.2, 0)$. At the stable interior equilibrium the system mainly consists of nomads. Among the territorials, the owners are in the majority. In the other two stable equilibria one of the two species is missing. If there are no nomads, the density of the territorial intruders is much greater than that of the territorial owners. Since the behavior of territorial intruders and nomads are similar one can say that the territorial intruders and the nomads substitute for one another.

Figure 2: The phase portrait of the system (2.4) with parameters of Example 2 (see the main text) when $b = 205/1000$ and $p = 0$. There are five equilibria marked by black discs on the diagram; each of them is hyperbolic and three of them are stable, that is, there is an ecological tristability. The coordinates of the equilibria in the ascending order of the first coordinates are $(0, 24.85)$, $(3.87, 7.64)$, $(18.97, 1.35)$, $(25.16, 0.36)$, $(28.2, 0)$. The situation is similar to that of Figure 1.

Figure 3: The phase portrait of the system (2.4) with parameters of Example 3 (see the main text) when $b = 21/100$. There are five equilibria marked by black discs on the diagram; each of them is hyperbolic and three of them are stable, that is, there is an ecological tristability. The coordinates of the equilibria in the ascending order of the first coordinates are $(0, 23.71)$, $(3.26, 7.89)$, $(19.57, 1.09)$, $(21.32, 0.82)$, $(28.2, 0)$. The situation is similar to that of Figure 1.

2.5.2 Ecologically stable coexistence of nomads and territorials (Examples 4-6)

Here again three examples are investigated. As stated above, the parameters are the same, even in the case of parameter b , the only distinction being in the strategy of the territorial individuals. The corresponding phase portraits of the differential equation system (2.4) with respect to these parameters are depicted in Figure 4-6. The phase portraits essentially agree with each other. There are three hyperbolic equilibria (see Table 2): two unstable equilibria on the axes and an interior locally asymptotically stable equilibrium. In the stable equilibrium the proportion of territorials and nomads is more balanced compared to Examples 1-3. Figure 4 shows the case when $p = 25/128$, Figure 5 when $p = 0$ and Figure 6 when $p = 1$. The value of p gains more significance if we investigate the resistance to mutants as we can see later.

Example	Equilibrium density		Eigenvalues		Stability
	x^*	y^*	λ_1	λ_2	
1.	0	23.85	-0.77	-0.058	l.a.s.
	3.33	7.86	-0.42	0.14	unstable
	19.51	1.12	-0.64	-0.20	l.a.s.
	21.76	0.77	-0.070	0.033	unstable
	28.2	0	-0.067	-0.047	l.a.s.
2.	0	24.85	-0.85	-0.062	l.a.s.
	3.87	7.64	-0.46	0.14	unstable
	18.97	1.35	-0.60	-0.23	l.a.s.
	25.16	0.36	-0.062	0.020	unstable
	28.2	0	-0.047	-0.030	l.a.s.
3.	0	23.71	-0.76	-0.058	l.a.s.
	3.26	7.89	-0.42	0.14	unstable
	19.57	1.09	-0.64	-0.20	l.a.s.
	21.32	0.82	-0.071	0.034	unstable
	28.2	0	-0.068	-0.047	l.a.s.
4.	0	12.06	-0.60	0.012	unstable
	10.1	5.5	-0.47	-0.085	l.a.s.
	18.6	0	-0.062	0.0875	unstable
5.	0	12.31	-0.64	0.011	unstable
	9.52	6.08	-0.47	-0.084	l.a.s.
	18.6	0	-0.062	0.10	unstable
6.	0	10.95	-0.47	0.015	unstable
	12.48	3.12	-0.56	-0.063	l.a.s.
	18.6	0	-0.062	0.036	unstable

Table 2: The ecological equilibria of Examples 1-6 in the non-negative quadrant with at least one species. As we can see, the linearization has non-zero eigenvalues at every equilibrium, that is, every equilibrium is hyperbolic. Abreviation: l.a.s. – locally asymptotically stable.

Figure 4: The phase portrait of the system (2.4) with the parameters of Example 4. There are three equilibria marked by black discs on the diagram; each of them is hyperbolic. The coordinates of the equilibria in the ascending order of the first coordinates are $(0, 12.06)$, $(10.1, 5.5)$, $(10.1, 0)$. The interior equilibrium is stable. The density of territorials and nomads are similar compared to that in the stable equilibrium in Examples 1-3 (see Figure 1-3). There is no interior unstable equilibrium. However, the equilibria on the axes are unstable, contrary to Examples 1-3.

Figure 5: The phase portrait of the system (2.4) with parameters of Example 5. There are three equilibria marked by black discs on the diagram; each of them is hyperbolic. The coordinates of the equilibria in the ascending order of the first coordinates are $(0, 12.31)$, $(9.52, 6.08)$, $(18.6, 0)$. The situation is similar to that of Figure 4.

Figure 6: The phase portrait of the system (2.4) with parameters of Example 6. There are three equilibria marked by black discs on the diagram; each of them is hyperbolic. The coordinates of the equilibria in the ascending order of the first coordinates are $(0, 10.95)$, $(12.48, 3.12)$, $(18.6, 0)$. The situation is similar to that of Figure 4.

3 Finding the Nash equilibrium

In the above we have considered a population where all territorial individuals play the strategy p in the owning position. This in turn leads to a specific stable value for each of x and y . We now consider invasion of the population by a different type of territorial which selects strategy q . When can p resist invasion from such a q ? A necessary condition for this to occur is for p to be a Nash equilibrium.

3.1 The mutant fitness function

We consider the fitness of a p individual and a q individual in an infinitely large population of resident p individuals in which a q individual appears.

We have found the fitness $G(x, y)$ of a p individual above. We get the fitness of a q individual if ϱ_a and ϱ_r with respect to p is replaced by ϱ_a and ϱ_r with respect to q which are denoted by $\hat{\varrho}_a$ and $\hat{\varrho}_r$ throughout this section. Generally, we use the notation “ $\hat{}$ ” if the given function belongs to the q territorials, e.g. $\hat{G}(x, y)$ denotes the fitness of a q territorial.

The distinction between \hat{G} and G derives from the fact that the time spent in the patroller/predator state is distinct for a q and a p territorial. Note that we again calculate an expected fitness for the q territorial in a foraging season because the q individual spends the part of the foraging season in intruder position and the other part in the owner position.

For our q individual, its mean fitness will be determined by the proportion of time that it spends in the owner and intruder states, and its mean payoff rate in each of these states. A q territorial and a p territorial are indistinguishable in the intruder position, so the fitness of a q territorial in the intruder position is the same as that of a p territorial in the intruder position. However, the ratio of time spent in the intruder position to that spent in the owner position can be distinguished with respect to p and q territorials. Therefore we calculate the expected duration from becoming an intruder until acquiring a territory and the expected duration from becoming an owner until losing the territory.

Specifically we have: *the fitness of a q territorial*:

$$\hat{G}(y) = \frac{\hat{T}_i \hat{G}_i + \hat{T}_o \hat{G}_o}{\hat{T}_i + \hat{T}_o}, \quad (3.1)$$

where:

\hat{T}_i is the expected length of time a q -individual spends in the intruder state between successive visits to the owner state;

\hat{T}_o is the expected length of time a q -individual spends in the owner state between successive visits to the intruder state;

\hat{G}_i is the expected payoff per unit time for a q -individual in the intruder state;

\hat{G}_o is the expected payoff per unit time for a q -individual in the owner state.

3.2 The four fitness components

Accordingly, we calculate the time spent expectedly in the intruder position from losing a territory until acquiring a new territory and the time that passes from acquiring a territory until losing it.

3.2.1 Time in the intruder position

An intruder encounters an (active) owner with rate λ_o . After this event the intruder becomes an owner providing that it wins, otherwise it continues its life as an intruder. The probability that an event is an encounter event is $\lambda_o/(\lambda_o + \lambda_h)$. Therefore the probability that the encounter event is

the n -th event is $[\lambda_h/(\lambda_o + \lambda_h)]^{n-1} \lambda_o/(\lambda_o + \lambda_h)$. So the expected number of events until the end of the first encounter event is

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n \left(\frac{\lambda_h}{\lambda_o + \lambda_h} \right)^{n-1} \frac{\lambda_o}{\lambda_o + \lambda_h} = \frac{\lambda_o + \lambda_h}{\lambda_o}.$$

Since every event is a prey event until the first encounter event the expected length of time that passes until the end of the first encounter event is

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{\lambda_h}{\lambda_o + \lambda_h} \right)^{n-1} \frac{\lambda_o}{\lambda_o + \lambda_h} \left[\frac{n}{\lambda_o + \lambda_h} + (n-1)t_h + t_l \right] \\ = \frac{1}{\lambda_o} + \frac{\lambda_h}{\lambda_o} t_h + t_l. \end{aligned}$$

Note that this result is natural: If we start a clock when the territorial becomes an intruder the encounter event expectedly happens at time $1/\lambda_o$. During the $1/\lambda_o$ length of time a prey event occurs λ_h/λ_o times.

Recall that λ_o is the rate of encountering an active owner. By (2.6), an active owner is in the patroller state with probability $\pi \varrho_a / [\pi \varrho_a + (1-\pi) \varrho_a] = p$ and in the predator state with probability $1-p$, respectively. Accordingly, the probability that the intruder wins is

$$p(1 - \alpha_a) + (1 - p)(1 - \alpha_r),$$

so the intruder has on average $1/[p(1 - \alpha_a) + (1 - p)(1 - \alpha_r)]$ fights until its first win. Then it becomes an owner. Therefore, the time (denoted by \hat{T}_i) spent in the intruder position from becoming an intruder until becoming an owner is

$$\hat{T}_i = \frac{1}{p(1 - \alpha_a) + (1 - p)(1 - \alpha_r)} \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_o} + \frac{\lambda_h}{\lambda_o} t_h + t_l \right).$$

3.2.2 Time in the owner position

In the owner position, the territorial can be in the patroller or in the predator state, respectively. First, we have to determine the time spent in the different states. The probability of winning a fight in the patroller state is α_a while, in the predator state, it is α_r . If a q -territorial is active (so is searching) then it is in the patroller state with probability q . Accordingly, when it gets involved in a fight, it loses its territory with probability $q(1 - \alpha_a) + (1 - q)(1 - \alpha_r)$ and, consequently, the expected number of fights until this occurs is $1/[q(1 - \alpha_a) + (1 - q)(1 - \alpha_r)]$. A reconsideration event is due to a fight with probability $\lambda_i/(\lambda_r + \lambda_i)$, so there are on average

$$\hat{R} := \left(\frac{\lambda_r + \lambda_i}{\lambda_i} \right) \frac{1}{q(1 - \alpha_a) + (1 - q)(1 - \alpha_r)}$$

reconsiderations from becoming an owner until losing the territory.

We now calculate the time taken from becoming an owner until losing the territory. The expected time between two reconsiderations is $1/(\lambda_r + \lambda_i)$ if the owner is in the patroller state and there is no fight, and $1/(\lambda_r + \lambda_i) + \lambda_h t_h/(\lambda_r + \lambda_i)$ if the owner is in the predator state and there is no fight (if there is a fight then the expected duration of the regeneration should be added to the previous durations). Since there are \hat{R} reconsiderations until losing the territory from which on average $q\hat{R}$ end up with a choice of the patroller strategy and there are on average $1/[q(1 - \alpha_a) + (1 - q)(1 - \alpha_r)]$

fights, the expected time \hat{T}_o from becoming an owner until losing the territory is

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{T}_o &= q\hat{R}\frac{1}{\lambda_r + \lambda_i} + (1-q)\hat{R}\frac{1 + \lambda_h t_h}{\lambda_r + \lambda_i} + \frac{1}{q(1 - \alpha_a) + (1-q)(1 - \alpha_r)} t_w \\ &= \frac{\hat{R}}{\lambda_r + \lambda_i} + (1-q)\hat{R}\frac{\lambda_h t_h}{\lambda_r + \lambda_i} + \frac{t_w}{q(1 - \alpha_a) + (1-q)(1 - \alpha_r)} \\ &= \frac{1}{q(1 - \alpha_a) + (1-q)(1 - \alpha_r)} \left[\frac{1}{\lambda_i} + (1-q)\frac{\lambda_h}{\lambda_i} t_h + t_w \right].\end{aligned}$$

3.2.3 Fitness in the intruder position

Since there is no distinction between a p and a q territorial in the intruder position their fitnesses are identical. So, by (2.7), we have

$$\hat{G}_i = -d - c_{nt}x - c_{tt}y + D_i.$$

3.2.4 Fitness in the owner position

In this case the distinctions between the fitnesses of p and q individuals derive from the distinctions in the direct interactions. The cost of maintenance and indirect interactions is the same for both strategies, $-d - c_{nt}x - c_{tt}y$.

To get the term in the fitness deriving from the direct interactions we should only repeat the calculation made for the p territorials but with respect to the time that passes from becoming an owner until losing the territory. The constant background intake rate b is present now too. We have seen previously there are $1/[q(1 - \alpha_a) + (1-q)(1 - \alpha_r)]$ winning fights with negative intake $-c_w$. When a territorial owner is defeated, the negative intake of the defeat is already considered in the intruder position; also, when an intruder wins a fight, the negative intake of the winning fight is considered in the owner position. In addition to this negative intake the intake from hunting in the predator position must be considered; this is

$$(1-q)\hat{R}\frac{\lambda_h i_h}{\lambda_r + \lambda_i}.$$

So the fitness in the owner position is

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{G}_o &= -d - c_{nt}x - c_{tt}y + b + \frac{-\frac{1}{q(1-\alpha_a)+(1-q)(1-\alpha_r)}c_w + (1-q)\hat{R}\frac{\lambda_h i_h}{\lambda_r + \lambda_i}}{\frac{1}{q(1-\alpha_a)+(1-q)(1-\alpha_r)} \left[\frac{1}{\lambda_i} + (1-q)\frac{\lambda_h}{\lambda_i} t_h + t_w \right]} \\ &= -d - c_{nt}x - c_{tt}y + b + \frac{-c_w + (1-q)\frac{\lambda_h i_h}{\lambda_i}}{\frac{1}{\lambda_i} + (1-q)\frac{\lambda_h}{\lambda_i} t_h + t_w} \\ &= -d - c_{nt}x - c_{tt}y + b + \frac{-\lambda_i c_w + (1-q)\lambda_h i_h}{1 + (1-q)\lambda_h t_h + \lambda_i t_w}.\end{aligned}$$

Observe that $\hat{G}_o + d + (x+y)c_i$ agrees with $\pi D_a + (1-\pi)D_r$ if q is replaced by p in $\hat{G}_o + d + c_{nt}x + c_{tt}y$.

3.3 Calculating the fitness

We now substitute the above four terms into the fitness function (3.2). We note that this is a linear rational function in q . Indeed,

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{G} &= -d - c_{nt}x - c_{tt}y + \frac{\hat{T}_i D_i}{\hat{T}_i + \hat{T}_o} + \frac{\hat{T}_o}{\hat{T}_i + \hat{T}_o} \left(b + \frac{-\lambda_i c_w + (1-q)\lambda_h i_h}{1 + (1-q)\lambda_h t_h + \lambda_i t_w} \right) \\
&= b - d - c_{nt}x - c_{tt}y + \frac{\hat{T}_i(D_i - b) + \hat{T}_o \cdot \left(\frac{-\lambda_i c_w + (1-q)\lambda_h i_h}{1 + (1-q)\lambda_h t_h + \lambda_i t_w} \right)}{\hat{T}_i + \hat{T}_o} \\
&= b - d - c_{nt}x - c_{tt}y + \frac{\hat{T}_i(D_i - b)[q(1 - \alpha_a) + (1-q)(1 - \alpha_r)] + \left[-c_w + (1-q)\frac{\lambda_h}{\lambda_i} i_h \right]}{\hat{T}_i[q(1 - \alpha_a) + (1-q)(1 - \alpha_r)] + \left[\frac{1}{\lambda_i} + (1-q)\frac{\lambda_h}{\lambda_i} t_h + t_w \right]}, \quad (3.2)
\end{aligned}$$

which immediately shows that \hat{G} is a linear rational function in q .

3.4 Nash equilibria

In what follows we write $\hat{G}(q, p)$ instead of \hat{G} defined in the previous section where p denotes the resident strategy and q denotes the mutant strategy.

Consider a strategy p . Let (x^*, y^*) be an asymptotically stable equilibrium of the dynamics (2.4) with territorials following strategy p . Then the triplet (p, x^*, y^*) or, by abuse of notation, p , is a (density dependent) **Nash equilibrium** (NE for short) if $\hat{G}(q, p) \leq \hat{G}(p, p)$ for every $q \neq p$ close enough to p . If the inequality is strict, then p is said to be a strict NE. (Note that $\hat{G}(q, p) = \hat{G}(q, p, x^*, y^*)$, that is, \hat{G} should be considered at $x = x^*$ and $y = y^*$ when the relation between $\hat{G}(q, p)$ and $\hat{G}(p, p)$ is investigated.)

We can re-write expression (3.2) as

$$\hat{G}(q, p) = \frac{a_{11}(p) + a_{12}(p)q}{a_{21}(p) + a_{22}(p)q} + a_3(p). \quad (3.3)$$

A Nash equilibrium is a best response to itself, and so equation (3.3) must be maximised over q at $q = p$. We thus have:

$p = 0$ is a Nash equilibrium if $a_{12}(0)a_{21}(0) - a_{11}(0)a_{22}(0) \leq 0$,

$p = 1$ is a Nash equilibrium if $a_{12}(1)a_{21}(1) - a_{11}(1)a_{22}(1) \geq 0$,

$0 < p < 1$ is a Nash equilibrium if $a_{12}(p)a_{21}(p) - a_{11}(p)a_{22}(p) = 0$. This condition is equivalent to having $\frac{\partial}{\partial q} \hat{G}(q, p)_{q=p} = 0$ due to the fact that \hat{G} is a linear rational function in q so that the derivative w.r.t q can be 0 only if the numerator of \hat{G} is a constant multiple of the denominator. The potential problem of the denominator of \hat{G} having a root on $[0, 1]$ does not arise, since from (3.2) we see that the denominator of \hat{G} is positive for any $q \in [0, 1]$.

4 Evolutionary stability

Below we consider two concepts of stability for our solutions, which we introduce in Section 4.1. The second of these, in terms of its definition and assumptions, is more realistic for our system.

4.1 Mixed solutions

All mixed strategy solutions p must satisfy

$$a_{12}(p)a_{21}(p) - a_{11}(p)a_{22}(p) = 0. \quad (4.1)$$

4.1.1 Convergence stability

Consider a mixed strategy p . Let (x^*, y^*) be an interior equilibrium of the dynamics (2.4) with respect to the strategy p , that is, $x^* > 0$, $y^* > 0$ and $F(p, x^*, y^*) = G(p, x^*, y^*) = 0$. Then by the implicit function theorem (see e.g. Theorem 9.28 (p. 224) in Rudin, 1976) there is a neighbourhood \mathcal{N} of p and a unique (continuously differentiable) function $(x^*(q), y^*(q))$ defined on \mathcal{N} such that $x^*(p) = x^*$, $y^*(p) = y^*$ and $F(x^*(q), y^*(q)) = G(x^*(q), y^*(q)) = 0$ for every $q \in \mathcal{N}$ (Lemma 2 in Cressman and Garay, 2003b). In our context, the function $(x^*(q), y^*(q))$ is called the **stationary density surface**².

The mixed strategy p (more precisely the triplet (p, x^*, y^*) if we emphasize the density dependence) is *convergence stable* if and only if the equilibrium condition (4.1) is satisfied, together with

$$\frac{d}{dr} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial q} \hat{G}(q, r) \Big|_{q=r} \right)_{r=p} < 0. \quad (4.2)$$

This is equivalent to having (4.1) satisfied and

$$\frac{d}{dr} (a_{12}(r)a_{21}(r) - a_{11}(r)a_{22}(r))_{r=p} < 0. \quad (4.3)$$

This means that within some neighbourhood the population strategy would evolve towards any strategy that satisfies the above conditions, and so in any case with a unique NE which is convergence stable, evolution would take a population starting from any strategy other than p to p .

It is important to emphasize when we investigate the convergence stability of a strategy p that we consider the function \hat{G} on the stationary density surface $(x^*(r), y^*(r))$ defined in a neighbourhood of p even if this is suppressed in the notation, that is, $\hat{G} = \hat{G}(q, r, x^*(r), y^*(r))$ in (4.2).

We shall consider an alternative definition of resistance to invasion by mutant strategies.

4.1.2 Density dependent ESSs (DDESS)

In the above definitions, we have not considered the population dynamics explicitly, only through the stationary density surface. We do this below.

The definition of density dependent ESS is a dynamic approach to stability. Our definition here follows the work of Cressman and Garay (2003b) in which a possible extension of the notion of the one species frequency dependent ESS (Maynard Smith, 1982) is discussed for the multi species density dependent system.

Consider a resident system of nomad and territorials. Let p be the strategy of the resident territorials. As before, denote by x and y , respectively, the density of nomads and resident territorials, with fitness functions F and G , respectively. Assume that some mutant territorials using strategy q appear in the population with density z and fitness function H (see the definition of F , G and H for $z > 0$ in Appendix A.2). Then the evolution of this system is described by the extended dynamics

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x} &= xF(x, y, z), \\ \dot{y} &= yG(x, y, z), \\ \dot{z} &= zH(x, y, z). \end{aligned} \quad (4.4)$$

From this point of view, the dynamics (2.4) can be called the resident system. Let $x^* = x^*(p)$, $y^* = y^*(p)$ be a positive equilibrium of the resident system (2.4). (p, x^*, y^*) is a *density dependent evolutionarily stable strategy* (DDESS) if

²There is in general more than one equilibrium for a given p and parameters. The stationary density surface can be considered at any of the equilibria (if the condition of the implicit function theorem are satisfied) but it is clear from the context where the stationary density surface is considered.

- (i) (x^*, y^*) is an asymptotically stable state of the resident dynamics (2.4) and
- (ii) whenever q is a strategy close enough to p but different from p , then $(x^*, y^*, 0)$ is an asymptotically stable rest point of the extended dynamics (4.4),

where “close enough to p ” means the existence of a $\delta > 0$ such that $|q - p| < \delta$. Thus an equilibrium density (x^*, y^*) is always associated with a DDESS but if this density is clear from the context we often suppress it and only say that p is a DDESS. We demonstrate how to show that a strategy is a DDESS in Appendix A.1.

4.2 Pure solutions

For the pure strategies $p = 0$ and $p = 1$ we have the following conditions for a strict Nash equilibrium. Strict Nash equilibria are also convergence stable and DDESS solutions as described above. Note that for pure strategies the non-strict equilibria are *non-generic* (see e.g. Broom and Rychtář, 2013) and so we do not consider these here further. $p = 0$ is a strict Nash equilibrium if

$$a_{12}(0)a_{21}(0) - a_{11}(0)a_{22}(0) < 0. \quad (4.5)$$

$p = 1$ is a strict Nash equilibrium if

$$a_{12}(1)a_{21}(1) - a_{11}(1)a_{22}(1) > 0. \quad (4.6)$$

It is possible to have one, both or neither of these solutions, as we see in Section 4.3.

4.3 Examples

Here we return to the examples given in Section 2.5. We have seen that each of the examples have an interior equilibrium. We investigate what occurs if a small amount of mutant territorials appear in the ecosystem of nomads and territorials at the interior equilibrium. We calculate the fitness of mutants according to Section 3.1. This intuitively describes the case when the resident population is infinitely large compared to the mutant subpopulation, so the density of mutants is practically zero. Furthermore, we get a suggestion of what one should expect in relation to the stability introduced in Section 4.1.1 and 4.1.2.

4.3.1 Evolutionary stability of a strategy in the ecologically stable interior equilibrium (Examples 1-3)

We proceed as follows. We investigate each example at three values of the resident strategy, namely, when the resident strategy is either of the two pure strategies ($p = 0$ or 1 , that is, the pure predator or the pure patroller strategy, respectively) and when the resident strategy is a mixed strategy suitably chosen. Then we plot the mutant fitness calculated according to Section 3.1 as a function of the mutant strategy q . Consequently, a figure related to a given example depicts three graphs. Comparing the slope of the graphs we can infer the stability property of a given resident strategy from the evolutionary viewpoint.

In Example 1 (when $b = 21/100$) the chosen mixed resident strategy is $p = 15475/19208$. At this value of the resident strategy any mutant proves neutral since its fitness agrees with the fitness of a resident, that is, the graph of the mutant fitness as a function of q is constant (the green solid line on Figure 7). Actually, starting from the formula (3.2) we have solved an equation for p to find a resident mixed strategy for which the mutant strategies are neutral if the residents are at the interior ecological equilibrium found in Section 2.5. This also means that p is a (density dependent) NE.

If the resident strategy is the pure predator strategy, that is, $p = 0$ then the graph of the mutant fitness increases in q as shown in Figure 7 (the blue dashed graph). So any kind of mutant can invade into the population of pure predators.

If the resident strategy is the pure patroller strategy, that is, $p = 1$ then the graph of the mutant fitness decreases in q as it shown on Figure 7 (the orange dotted graph). So any kind of mutant can invade into the population of pure patrollers.

Comparing the three examples of the value of the resident strategy one can expect that the resident population of individuals following the mixed strategy p can resist (a small amount of) mutants. Indeed this is the case as the line slopes of any p smaller (larger) than this critical value are positive (negative) in q , so that we have convergence stability. We can also check formally that the strategy is both convergence stable and DDESS. To see convergence stability we substitute appropriate values into (4.2) to get

$$\frac{d}{dr} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial q} \hat{G}(q, r) \Big|_{q=r} \right)_{r=p} \approx -0.0010 < 0,$$

that is, the condition of convergence stability is satisfied. As regards density dependent stability we follow the process described after Lemma A.1 in the Appendix and get that

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial q} B(q) \Big|_{q=p} = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial^2}{\partial q^2} B(q) \Big|_{q=p} \approx -0.018 < 0,$$

that is, strategy p is also a DDESS (see Table 3).

We remark that the stable equilibrium with no nomads proves unstable from an evolutionary point of view. It can be invaded by any mutant with strategy $q > p$ (see Table 3).

Figure 7: The fitness of mutants in the resident monomorphic population of individuals following strategy p at the stable interior ecological equilibrium of Example 1 ($b = 21/10$, see Section 2.5 and Figure 1). The fitness of a mutant following strategy q is calculated by formula (3.2). If the strategy of resident individuals is $p = 15475/19208$ then every kind of mutant has the same fitness, that is, every mutant type is neutral against the resident phenotype. Therefore the fitness is constant in q (green solid graph). If the strategy of the resident population is the pure predator strategy then the fitness of mutants is increasing in q (blue dashed graph) which shows that any mutant type can invade the resident population. Also, if the strategy of the individuals of the resident population is the pure patroller strategy then the fitness of mutants is decreasing in q (orange dotted graph), so the resident population cannot resist any kind of mutant again. The three graphs together suggest that the mixed strategy p is an evolutionarily stable strategy.

In Examples 2 and 3 as well, the fitness of the mutants as a function of q has been compared with respect to the previous three values of the resident strategy. The only distinction in Example

2 compared to Example 1 is that the value of parameter b is a little smaller, being $205/1000$. This means that the steady contribution of having a territory is smaller than in Example 1. Therefore it seems rewarding to hunt more and this conjecture is supported by the three graphs on Figure 8. Every graph is decreasing in q . Consequently, the predator strategy always proves the most remunerative independently of the strategy of the resident individuals.

The situation in Example 3 is similar in form to that in Example 2, but yielding the reverse outcome. Here $b = 215/1000$, that is a bit greater than in Example 1. Therefore one can expect that it is worth hunting to a lesser extent and patrolling instead. Indeed, the graphs on Figure 9 support this expectation, for the fitness of mutants as a function of q increases in q independently of the strategy of the resident individuals. As a consequence, the highest fitness always belongs to the pure patroller strategy.

Accordingly, Examples 2 and 3 are examples when a pure strategy resists mutants. As Table 3 shows both equilibria are not only convergence stable and DDESS, but strict NE.

We remark that the stable equilibrium with no nomads is unstable in Example 2 (it can be invaded by any mutants following a strategy $q > 0$) while it is a strict NE in Example 3.

Figure 8: The fitness of mutants in the resident monomorphic population of individuals following strategy p at the stable interior ecological equilibrium of Example 2 ($b = 205/1000$, see Section 2.5 and Figure 2). The fitness of a mutant following strategy q is calculated by formula (3.2). The fitness of mutants is a decreasing function of q independently of the strategy of individuals of the resident population. Consequently, the most rewarding strategy is always the pure predator strategy suggesting not only the evolutionary stability of this strategy but that it is a strict NE.

Figure 9: The fitness of mutants in the resident monomorphic population of individuals following strategy p at the stable interior ecological equilibrium of Example 3 ($b = 215/1000$, see Section 2.5 and Figure 3). The fitness of a mutant following strategy q is calculated by formula (3.2). The fitness of mutants is an increasing function of q independently of the strategy of individuals of the resident population. Consequently, the most rewarding strategy is always the pure patroller strategy suggesting not only the evolutionary stability of this strategy but that it is a strict NE.

4.3.2 Evolutionarily instability of a mixed strategy in an ecologically stable interior equilibrium (Examples 4-6)

As in Examples 1-3, the fitness of mutants is investigated with respect to three distinct values of the strategy of resident individuals: for the two pure strategies and for the mixed strategy $p = 25/128$. The mixed strategy has again been chosen in such a way that every kind of mutants proves neutral against the resident population of individuals following p at the ecological equilibrium found in Section 2.5 (green horizontal graph on Figure 10). This also means that strategy $p = 25/128$ is a (density dependent) NE. However, contrary to Example 1, if the resident strategy is the pure predator strategy ($p = 0$) then the fitness of mutant as a function of q is decreasing in q (blue dashed graph on Figure 10), so the resident pure predators have the highest fitness showing that

Example	Equilibrium density		$\frac{\partial}{\partial q} \hat{G}(q, p) _{q=p}$	$\frac{d}{dr} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial q} \hat{G}(q, r) \Big _{q=r} \right) \Big _{r=p}$	$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial q^2} B(q) _{q=p}$	Evolutionary stability
	x^*	y^*				
1.	0	23.85	0.0019 > 0	-	-	unstable from the right
	19.51	1.12	0	-0.010 < 0	-0.018 < 0	CS, DDES
2.	0	24.86	0.00026 > 0	-	-	unstable from the right
	18.97	1.35	-0.0037 < 0	-	-	strict NE
3.	0	23.71	0.0045 > 0	-	-	strict NE
	19.57	1.09	0.041	-	-	strict NE
4.	$\frac{101}{10}$	$\frac{11}{2}$	0	0.0020 > 0	0.0012 > 0	unstable NE
5.	9.52	6.08	$-\frac{1}{1975} < 0$	-	-	strict NE
6.	12.48	3.12	$\frac{103}{5075} > 0$	-	-	strict NE

Table 3: Investigation of the evolutionary stability of the stable ecological equilibria in which the density of territorials is positive. p denotes the strategy of the resident territorials. We recall that in Example 1 $p = 15475/19208$ and $b = 21/100$, in Example 2 $p = 0$ and $b = 205/1000$ while in Example 3 $p = 1$ and $b = 215/1000$. We note that in all cases above we have $y^* > 1$, as otherwise there are no contests between territorials, and the value of p , and any corresponding mutant q , would be irrelevant. Abbreviations: NE – Nash equilibrium, CS – convergence stable, DDES – density dependent evolutionary stable. “unstable from the right” means that the resident system can only be invaded by mutants following a strategy $q > p$.

the population of pure predators resists small amount of mutants. This is also true for all resident strategies below the critical value of $25/128$. Also, if the resident strategy is the pure patroller strategy ($p = 1$) then the fitness of mutants as a function of q is increasing in q (orange dotted graph on Figure 10), so the resident pure patrollers have the highest fitness showing that the population of pure patrollers resists small amount of mutants. This is again also true for all resident strategies above the critical value. In summary, Examples 4-6 provide a set of parameters with a mixed strategy which is unstable from an evolutionary perspective; its stable resident equilibrium can be invaded by any mutants following a strategy q distinct from $25/128$, and pure strategies which are evolutionarily stable (see Table 3).

Figure 10: The fitness of mutants in the resident monomorphic population of individuals following strategy p at the stable interior ecological equilibrium values of Examples 4-6 (see Section 2.5 and Figures 4-6). The fitness of a mutant following strategy q is calculated by formula (3.2). If the strategy of resident individuals is $p = 25/128$ then every kind of mutant has the same fitness, that is, every mutant type is neutral against the resident phenotype. Therefore the fitness is constant in q (green solid graph). If the strategy of the resident population is the pure predator strategy then the fitness of mutants is decreasing in q (blue dashed graph) contrary to Examples 1-3 which shows that the resident population can resist any kind of mutant. If the strategy of the individuals of the resident population is the pure patroller strategy then the fitness of mutants is increasing in q (orange dotted graph) contrary to Examples 1-3, so the resident population again resists any kind of mutant. The three graphs together suggest that the mixed strategy $p = 25/128$ is evolutionarily unstable while the pure strategies are both evolutionarily stable, moreover, strict NE. Indeed this is so, as any resident strategy below (above) the critical value $p = 25/128$ is also decreasing (increasing) in q .

5 Discussion

In this paper we have considered a model of territorial behaviour, where territory owners must defend their territories from intruders who in turn wish to take over the territory. A territory has a value to its owner while it is occupied, but defence comes at a cost both in terms of time and risk of injury/energy cost. Owners have a choice of a more active patrolling defence, which was more costly, but have a greater chance of repelling intruders, or a less active defence, the "predator" state, where their priority is foraging. The effectiveness of each strategy depends upon the rewards available compared to the different costs, but also crucial is the density of the population, influenced by indirect intractions caused by underlying environmental quality. The population also consists of an alternative type of individual, nomads, who do not fight for territories, but nonetheless have an important indirect impact through their use of resources.

We have seen that the strategies adopted by the owners affect the population size (see Figures 4-6), caused by a reduction in their resource intake level, and thus has an indirect influence on the effectiveness of the owner strategy. Depending upon the parameters, we thus saw cases where there is a stable pure defensive strategy, where both pure strategies are stable, or where a mixed defensive strategy, sometimes patrolling and sometimes not, is stable. Similarly there are cases where the nomads are extinct, and others where there is a large population of this type.

The main novelty of our work is that in the framework of game theoretical modelling, we take account not only of energetic cost of the defence of a territory but also the time constraints of different activities and the density dependence of the interactions, as well. The time constraints and the density dependence of fitness are linked, since the time duration of territory defence depends upon

the density of intruders. For instance, European Jays (*Garrulus glandarius L.*) in Sweden occupy territories which exhibit the highest breeding success (Henrik 1990), but in the Maremma Natural Park in Italy this species is non-territorial. In the latter case the resources are very abundant, and the density of birds is high, thus the cost of defending the territory against all intruders would be higher than the benefit of owning a territory (Rolando et al. 1995).

In each of the following paragraphs we introduce a scenario, and give real biological cases for which it applies.

Territorials outperform nomads: In the ecological tristable examples, one of the locally asymptotically stable rest points of the population density dependent dynamics is an equilibrium where there are no nomads (Figure 1-3). This occurs, for example, when the territory is necessary for reproduction, like the spotted hyena (Kruuk 1972), Tengmalm’s owl (Korpimaki 1988) and eurasian beaver (Rosell et al. 1998).

Nomads outperform territorials: Territoriality is only shown by a minority of species, for instance some well-known examples from non-territorial animals are migratory ungulates (e.g. wildebeest, reindeer), herding fish (e.g. herring) and colony breeding birds (Burger and Gochfeld 1994). Moreover, the home range is not always defended, for instance Grant et al. (1992) reported 11 undefending carnivores species from 23 species and 23 undefending ungulates from 62 species. So territoriality is not always evolutionarily stable behaviour.

Coexistence of territorials and nomads: In the ecological tristable examples and in the example with a single stable equilibrium there is a locally asymptotically stable interior rest point of the population density dependent dynamics, where the territorial and nomad phenotypes coexist. We already mentioned some biological examples for this situation, namely the side-blotched lizard (*Uta stansburiana*) (Sinervo and Lively 1996, Sinervo et al. 2000), sunfish and salmon (e.g. Gross 1984 and references therein, Gross and Charnov 1980). In each case the territorial phenotype belongs to our patroller phenotype, moreover in these species the nomads have different genetically determined phenotypes to the territorials ones. For instance, male bluegill sunfish has two alternative mating strategies: cuckoldry or parental care. Cuckolder males first mature at age two and follow a developmental sequence of sneaking and then mimicking female behavior to deceptively gain access to spawnings. Males who become parental (construct and defend nests) delay maturation until age seven (Gross and Charnov 1980). Although common cuckoos (*Cuculus canorus*) do not show parental care, the males are territorial and aggressively defend their territories. According to the dear enemy phenomenon (Fisher 1954) the territory owners tolerate familiar male neighbours living on adjacent territories more than unfamiliar “floating” males. Here the owners are the older males and floaters younger males who try to copulate with the females living on the owners’ territories (Moskát et al. 2017).

From the perspective of evolution, we point out that in these cases in the interior equilibrium, there are either mixed territorial ESS, i.e. the ESS is a mixture of the patrolling and predator strategy, see Figure 7, or a unique pure territorial ESSs, i.e. either patrolling see Figure 8 or predator see Figure 9). Moreover, it can be possible to have evolutionary bistability when both the pure patroller and the pure predator strategies are strict NE. There are many biological examples for the case of the mixed ESS, e.g. lions (Schaller 1972) wolves (Hayes 2010), and damselflies (Golab et al. 2017). As regards the pure ESSs, from a biological point of view, the difference between our patroller and predator pure strategies is that the former has an extra cost in territorial defence such as birds’ song, which has various behavioural patterns, depending upon the ecological conditions. For example, tropical birds use song for breeding and non-breeding territorial defence. But in other species the song has two different functions: Song restricted to males is used for the defense of breeding territories and to attract females (females may be unable to range male song). Different songs are used to defend non-breeding territories. Moreover, where songs are used for non-breeding territorial defense both sexes sing (Morton and Stutchbury 2012). Finally, we mention an example which corresponds to our “predator” strategy: the red-footed falcon (*Falco vespertinus*) defends its

territory, but does not sing (Purger 2001).

Our theoretical model draws attention to the fact that we should take time constraints and the density dependence of fitness into account to gain a deeper understanding of territoriality. In future work there are two potential main directions. Firstly a more detailed adaptive dynamic analysis could be applied to our model. Indeed, the exact relationship between convergence stability and density dependent stability for the model is still an open question. Secondly, in the second direction, more detailed mechanistic models based on the fact that a territory can provide benefits of different types for owner (e.g. food, mating opportunities) could be developed, potentially with different consequences. Using these biological details in a framework of mechanistic models, the competitive feature of territoriality can be investigated more fully. Three possible generalizations are: allowing the mortality rate of a non-owner to depend upon the ability of an owner to defend food; considering the classic side-blotched lizard population incorporating density-dependence; incorporating signalling behaviour of the owner, such as scent-marking and singing. In this latter case, there is the possibility of intruders being discouraged, depending upon the signal and if they trust that it is “honest”; this thus introduces strategic decisions for the intruders. There are a number of other possibilities, so there is much opportunity to develop the model further.

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A Appendix

A.1 Investigation of the evolutionary stability of a strategy

To check that a strategy is a DDESS means that we should investigate the asymptotic stability of infinitely many equilibria (to check that (x^*, y^*) is an asymptotic stable rest point of the resident system (2.4) and that $(x^*, y^*, 0)$ is an asymptotic stable rest point of the extended system (4.4) for any q close to p). The simplest case is when the resident ecological equilibrium (x^*, y^*) is hyperbolic with respect to the resident dynamics (2.4) while the equilibrium $(x^*, y^*, 0)$ is hyperbolic with respect to the extended dynamics (4.4). In our case this just means the hyperbolicity of (x^*, y^*) with respect to the resident dynamics and that $H(x^*, y^*, 0) < 0$.³ The situation is somewhat more difficult if the hyperbolicity does not hold somewhere. In this paper, we will meet such cases when the equilibrium (x^*, y^*) is hyperbolic with respect to the resident dynamics but $(x^*, y^*, 0)$ is not hyperbolic with respect to the extended dynamics any longer because $H(x^*, y^*, 0) = 0$, that is, the invading mutant strategy is selectively neutral with respect to the resident population. Then we can appeal for help to the following lemma.

Lemma A.1 (Lemma 2, Cressman and Garay (2003b)) *Assume that (x^*, y^*) is a locally asymptotic stable hyperbolic equilibrium with respect to the resident system (2.4) and $H(x^*, y^*, 0) = 0$. If*

$$\partial_z H - (\partial_x H, \partial_y H) \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \partial_x F & \partial_y F \\ \partial_x G & \partial_y G \end{pmatrix}^{-1} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \partial_z F \\ \partial_z G \end{pmatrix} \Big|_{(x,y,z)=(x^*,y^*,0)} < 0, \quad (\text{A.1})$$

³One can readily check that the eigenvalues of the Jacobian matrix of the extended dynamics (4.4) at the equilibrium $(x^*, y^*, 0)$ is just the two eigenvalues of the Jacobian matrix of the resident dynamics (2.4) at the equilibrium (x^*, y^*) and the value of $H(x^*, y^*, 0)$.

then $(x^*, y^*, 0)$ is also asymptotic stable with respect to the extended dynamics (4.4).

If the direction of the inequality in (A.1) is reversed, then $(x^*, y^*, 0)$ is unstable.

We can use the lemma to prove that a hyperbolic equilibrium (x^*, y^*) is a DDESS. Denote by $B(q)$ the left-hand side of formula (A.1) for a given q . (p, x^*, y^*) is a DDESS, if $B(p) = 0$ and B has a strict minimum in $q = p$. To see this, it is enough to check that $\partial_q B(q)_{q=p} = 0$ and $\frac{\partial^2}{\partial q^2} B(q)_{q=p} < 0$. If $\frac{\partial^2}{\partial q^2} B(q)_{q=p} > 0$, then (p, x^*, y^*) is evolutionarily unstable in the sense that any kind of mutant with strategy close enough to p can invade the resident population. We proceed this way in our examples.

If one of the densities in the resident equilibrium (x^*, y^*) is zero and the other is not, that is, $x^* = 0$ and $y^* > 0$ or $x^* > 0$ and $y^* = 0$, then the previous lemma changes as follows.

Lemma A.1' *Assume that $(0, y^*)$ is a hyperbolic equilibrium of the resident dynamics (2.4) that is $F(0, y^*) < 0$ and $\partial_y G(0, y^*) < 0$. If*

$$\partial_z H - \frac{\partial_y H \partial_z G}{\partial_y G} \Big|_{(x,y,z)=(0,y^*,0)} < 0,$$

then $(0, y^*, 0)$ is a locally asymptotic stable rest point of the extended dynamics (4.4). (The case $(x^*, 0)$ is similar, with only the role of x and y and the role of F and G , respectively, exchanged.)

The relationship between convergence stability and density dependent evolutionary stability is partially investigated in Cressman and Garay (2003b). However, in their assumptions there is an essential distinction to those of this article. To explain this distinction denote the stationary density surface defined in Section 4.1.1 as being of type I. We define the stationary density surface of type II as follows. Fix strategy p and strategy q such that $q \neq p$. Let (x^*, y^*) be an interior equilibrium of dynamics (2.4) with respect to p , that is, $F(x^*, y^*) = 0$, $G(x^*, y^*) = 0$ and introduce some mutants of strategy q with density $z (\geq 0)$ into this resident system. If the equilibrium (x^*, y^*) is hyperbolic, then, by the implicit function theorem, there is a $\delta = \delta(q) > 0$ and a unique function $(x_q^*(z), y_q^*(z))$ on $(-\delta, \delta)$ such that $F(x_q^*(z), y_q^*(z)) = G(x_q^*(z), y_q^*(z)) = 0$ for any $z \in (-\delta, \delta)$ (Lemma 2 in Cressman and Garay, 2003b). This function is the stationary density surface of type II with respect to q . Note that this function depends on q as emphasized by the subscript. While there is a single stationary density surface of type I which is a function of q , there is a continuum of stationary density surface of type II (namely one for every possible strategy different from the resident strategy) and each of them is a function of z .

Cressman and Garay (2003b) fixed a mutant strategy q and considered the polymorphic population of resident individuals following strategy p and mutant individuals following strategy q . Denote by y the density of the residents and by z the density of the mutants. Depending on the densities the mean strategy of the population is $r = r(y, z)$. Our function \hat{G} in the definition of convergence stability measures the fitness of a mutant individual following strategy q in the monomorphic population of individuals following strategy r at the density pair $(x^*(r), y^*(r))$ where $(x^*(r), y^*(r))$ is the stationary density surface of type I. Conversely, the function of Cressman and Garay (2003b) measures the fitness of a mutant individual following strategy q in the polymorphic population of resident individuals following strategy p and mutant individuals following strategy q at the density triplet $(x_q^*(z), y_q^*(z), z)$ where $(x_q^*(z), y_q^*(z))$ is the stationary density surface of type II with respect to strategy q . So their function in convergence stability agrees with our function H on the stationary density surface of type II with respect to strategy q . They showed that in this case convergence stability is equivalent to the asymptotic stability of $(x^*, y^*, 0)$ with respect to the extended dynamics (4.4) when the strategy of invaders is q . But this does not prove the equivalence of the convergence stability defined in Section 4.1.1 and density dependent evolutionary stability, since our function in convergence stability is distinct from that of Cressman and Garay (2003b). In addition, we would like $(x^*, y^*, 0)$ to be stable with respect to the extended dynamics (4.4) with respect to a continuum

of qs instead of a single q which is fixed in advance. So, the relationship of convergence stability and the density dependent evolutionary stability is an open question for our model.

A.2 The definition of the fitness functions with respect to a population with mutants

To investigate density dependent evolutionary stability one needs to investigate the extended equation (4.4) in which the following functions can be found: $F(x, y, z)$, $G(x, y, z)$ and $H(x, y, z)$ where F is the fitness of a nomad individual, G is the fitness of a resident territorial individual and H is the fitness of a mutant territorial individual in an ecological system in which the density of the nomads is x , the density of the resident territorials is y and the density of the mutant territorials is z . We shall assume that every mutant individual follows the same strategy. We give the definitions of the three functions here, which are similar to those when there are no mutants, the functions in dynamics (2.4); in particular, they are the extensions of those to $z \geq 0$.

Consider an ecological system in which the density of nomads is x , the density of territorial individuals following strategy p is y while those following strategy q is z . One can think of p as the resident strategy and q as the mutant strategy but their roles from a mathematical point of view are symmetric.

The case with more territorials than territories

First, we deal with the case where there are more territorial individuals than available territories, i.e. $y + z > 1$.

Denote by y_o the density of territorial owners following strategy p in the stationary state (we give below how to calculate y_o). Then the density of territorial owners following strategy q is $1 - y_o$.

The probability γ that a randomly chosen active owner loses in a fight is

$$\gamma = \frac{y_o \varrho_{o,p}}{y_o \varrho_{o,p} + (1 - y_o) \varrho_{o,q}} [p(1 - \alpha_a) + (1 - p)(1 - \alpha_r)] + \frac{(1 - y_o) \varrho_{o,q}}{y_o \varrho_{o,p} + (1 - y_o) \varrho_{o,q}} [q(1 - \alpha_a) + (1 - q)(1 - \alpha_r)]$$

where $(y_o \varrho_{o,p}) / (y_o \varrho_{o,p} + (1 - y_o) \varrho_{o,q})$ is the probability that an active owner is a resident while $((1 - y_o) \varrho_{o,q}) / (y_o \varrho_{o,p} + (1 - y_o) \varrho_{o,q})$ is the probability that an active owner is a mutant. Consequently, an intruder has expectation of being involved in $1/\gamma$ losing fights before it wins. The expected time passing from a losing fight until the next fight is

$$t_l + \frac{1}{\lambda_o} + \frac{\lambda_h}{\lambda_o} t_h$$

where t_l is the waiting time after a losing fight, $1/\lambda_o$ is the expected time necessary to encounter an active owner and $\frac{\lambda_h}{\lambda_o} t_h$ is the expected additional time which is spent handling prey items found before this encounter.

Hence the expected time passing from becoming an intruder until the first win is

$$T_i = \frac{1}{\gamma} \left(\frac{1 + \lambda_h t_h}{\lambda_o} + t_l \right).$$

Recall that the waiting time after a defeat in the owner position (which implies that the owner loses its territory and becomes an intruder) is already allocated to the intruder position while the waiting time after a win in the intruder position is already allocated to the owner position. (In the intruder position there is no distinction between the two strategies so it is not necessary to introduce separate functions $T_{i,p}$ and $T_{i,q}$. They are both equal to T_i .)

Similarly, we get the expected time passing from becoming an owner until the first defeat is

$$T_{o,p} = \frac{1}{p(1 - \alpha_a) + (1 - p)(1 - \alpha_r)} \left(\frac{1 + (1 - p)\lambda_h t_h}{\lambda_i} + t_w \right)$$

if the owner follows strategy p and

$$T_{o,q} = \frac{1}{q(1 - \alpha_a) + (1 - q)(1 - \alpha_r)} \left(\frac{1 + (1 - q)\lambda_h t_h}{\lambda_i} + t_w \right)$$

if the owner follows strategy q (the factors $(1 - p)$ and $(1 - q)$ before λ_h are derived from the fact that the owner reconsiders its state $(\lambda_r + 1)/\lambda_i$ times during the search for an active intruder and decides to be a predator in proportions $(1 - p)$ and $(1 - q)$, respectively, of the reconsiderations).

The value of y_o , if $y + z > 1$, is determined by the following equation:

$$\frac{T_{o,p}}{T_{o,p} + T_i} y + \frac{T_{o,q}}{T_{o,q} + T_i} z = 1. \quad (\text{A.2})$$

Recall that T_i depends on y_o through γ so the previous equation is really an equation in y_o .

Since the active proportion of a population agrees with the quotient of the time spent in the active state and the sum of the times spent in the active and inactive states we have

$$\varrho_i = \frac{\frac{1}{\gamma} \frac{1}{\lambda_o}}{\frac{1}{\gamma} \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_o} + \frac{\lambda_h t_h}{\lambda_o} \right) + t_l} = \frac{1}{1 + \lambda_o t_l + \lambda_h t_h}, \quad (\text{A.3})$$

$$\varrho_{o,p} = \frac{1}{1 + \lambda_i t_l + (1 - p)\lambda_h t_h}, \quad (\text{A.4})$$

$$\varrho_{o,q} = \frac{1}{1 + \lambda_i t_l + (1 - q)\lambda_h t_h}, \quad (\text{A.5})$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_o &= f \cdot (y_o \varrho_{o,p} + (1 - y_o) \varrho_{o,q}), \\ \lambda_i &= f \cdot (y + z - 1) \varrho_i. \end{aligned}$$

(Thus we have an equation system of equations (A.2)-(A.5) with the four unknowns y_o , ϱ_i , $\varrho_{o,p}$, $\varrho_{o,q}$.)

The expected intakes during the times T_i , $T_{o,p}$ and $T_{o,q}$ in turn are

$$\begin{aligned} I_i &= \frac{1}{\gamma} \left(\frac{\lambda_h}{\lambda_o} i_h - c_l \right), \\ I_{o,p} &= \frac{1}{p(1 - \alpha_a) + (1 - p)(1 - \alpha_r)} \left(\frac{(1 - p)\lambda_h}{\lambda_i} i_h - c_w \right), \\ I_{o,q} &= \frac{1}{q(1 - \alpha_a) + (1 - q)(1 - \alpha_r)} \left(\frac{(1 - q)\lambda_h}{\lambda_i} i_h - c_w \right). \end{aligned}$$

Hence the fitness of a territorial following strategy p is

$$G(x, y, z) = -d - c_{nt}x - c_{tt} \cdot (y + z) + \frac{y_o}{y} \frac{I_{o,p}}{T_{o,p}} + \frac{y - y_o}{y} \frac{I_i}{T_i}$$

while the fitness of a territorial following strategy q is

$$H(x, y, z) = -d - c_{nt}x - c_{tt} \cdot (y + z) + \frac{1 - y_o}{z} \frac{\hat{I}_{o,q}}{T_{o,q}} + \frac{1 + z - y_o}{z} \frac{I_i}{T_i}.$$

As regards the nomads we get the same formula as in (2.10), though λ_o depends not only on y , but also now z . In particular,

$$F(x, y, z) = -d - c_{nn}x - c_{tn}(y + z) + \frac{\lambda_h i_h - \lambda_o c_f}{1 + \lambda_o t_f + \lambda_h t_h}.$$

We remark that one can easily check that $H(x, y, 0) = \hat{G}$ in (3.2), $F(x, y, 0) = F(x, y)$ and $G(x, y, 0) = G(x, y)$ in (2.10).

The case where there are not more territorials than territories

Here we consider the simpler case when $y + z \leq 1$. Then every territorial is in the owner position and, consequently, there is no direct interactions among the territorial individuals, i.e. $\lambda_i = 0$. We have

$$\begin{aligned}\varrho_{o,p} &= \frac{1}{1 + (1-p)\lambda_h t_h}, \\ \varrho_{o,q} &= \frac{1}{1 + (1-q)\lambda_h t_h}, \\ \lambda_o &= (y\varrho_{o,p} + z\varrho_{o,q})f, \\ F(x, y, z) &= -d - c_{nn}x - c_{tn}(y+z) + \frac{\lambda_h i_h - \lambda_o c_f}{1 + \lambda_o t_f + \lambda_h t_h}, \\ G(x, y, z) &= -d - c_{nt}x - c_{tt}(y+z) + b + \frac{(1-p)\lambda_h i_h}{1 + (1-p)\lambda_h t_h}, \\ H(x, y, z) &= -d - c_{nt}x - c_{tt}(y+z) + b + \frac{(1-q)\lambda_h i_h}{1 + (1-q)\lambda_h t_h}.\end{aligned}$$

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